

Effective Image Fusion Technique based on Local Correlation Modeling in Wavelet Domain for Satellite Image Fusion

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Abstract--- Image fusion is the benefit process of information received from multiple domains. The aim of the image fusion technique is to extract the necessary data from the multiple images to generate an enhanced composite image. The fused images are to take less bandwidth and less time. Multispectral satellite images have several groups of low resolution and limited information. These groups merge into the fused image that contains common information for all groups, but the existing image fusion techniques are affected by the color degradation. The purpose of this study is to improve spectral and spatial data of satellite images using Local Correlation Modeling (LCM) in wavelet transform. It shows the superior performance than the existing color and the sharpening techniques.

Keywords--- Image Fusion, Local Correlation Modeling, Wavelet Transform, Satellite Images.

I. Introduction

Multispectral (MS) hyper-spectral satellite imagery consists of several bands that represent the differences in these images, but these groups are low and have limited resolutions related to gravity. So, to gain more ground-related applications, these MS images are improved by image processing methods [1]. The integration of images is one of the most effective methods for improving geometric imaging with a radiometric resolution, together with a lower resolution Panchromatic (PAN) image with a high resolution (16 bit) [2].

High resolution images are PAN and not very formal, but in greyscale. Conversely, MS data (five bands) has been set and therefore cannot get full comprehension of the image. This low quality band combines with PAN images for detailed data. The robustness of PAN remains the same image that is kept, but is a high quality image.

The combination of low resolution MS image and high quality PAN images provides full and complete image information. Contrast enhancement is one of the most advanced techniques to increase the intensity of the image by observing remotely with Gaussian histograms. Numerous PAN techniques for enhanced imaging, including alteration, characterization, and radiation are used. Ehlers fusion, projective hyper spherical and subtractive color space resolution merge tool, modified IHS resolution and wavelet resolution merge methods [3],[4].

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is one of the most effective techniques to minimize obscure and measured information in the input method, but the first and second PCA vectors are orthogonal, the first component is data variability and the most recent result. From the second information, the vector is horizontally to the first PCA component.

Likewise, all PCA components are horizontal. PCA can compress data. In saturated images, the same information is repeated in different groups, but separation cannot be done by analyzing the underlying component. Therefore, high quality statistics should be used to separate the details from satellite images [5].

II. Related Works

Recently man-made satellite image data is growing rapidly. Various techniques have been proposed for non-monitored data and radiometric adaptation techniques without extending to the highest level. Satellite image contains information on Earth surfaces.

Table 1: NOOVA Satellite bands

Channels	Band width(μm)	Spectral band
1	0.58-0.68	Visible
2	0.725-1.18	Near IR
3a	1.68-1.64	Mid IR
3b	3.55-3.93	Thermal IR
4	10.3-11.3	Thermal IR
5	11.5-12.5	Thermal IR

The national oceanic and atmospheric administration (NOAA) satellite receivers receive images in the form of advance very high resolution radiometer (AVHRR) data. NOAA AVHRR MS [6] visible light frequency satellite images from thermal infrared (IR) up to 1.09 μm with a five-channel spatial wavelength. Table 1 provides channel bandwidth availability. These personal MS bands have more clarity than the PAN satellite images [7].

Reflective methods are applied to all types of bands to reduce the size of the reflection. In PCA, each axis is orthogonal to each other.

Usually, the first formula episode has the maximum possible change of original image, and the second and third parts are not stored in previous protocol sections. By the traditional second-order statistics, the Gaussian noise is removed, however, higher-level multiplication and impulse noise images are analyzed using higher order statistics. Independent Component Analysis (ICA) is a statistical method of converting multidimensional random vector data into independent parts. The PCA only takes statistics of the second order of the consideration, but the ICA is an extension of the PCA to blind the separation of data from its linear mix. The component is a computational technique that divides the multi-variable code into subdivision. PCA has Eigen value of data using second-order statistics that apply to the Gaussian distribution.

Due to artificial limits, MS fusion algorithms have been developed in movies to produce positive effects. Average and wave filters for smoothing and multiplication and boron for surface detection have been proposed [8]. Brori transition (BT) have a specific trade generalization of color spectrum determination and color technology. Any imbalance between image distortions is indicated. Removal of image ratios on satellite images and the separate channel to reduce the effect of land illumination in principle production. Image smoothing, low and high pass filter, edge detection and improvement have been implemented[9].

When uneven, PAN and MS resolution can result from IHS-fusion band imbalances[10]. The BT standard method is one of the color generalization and spectrum teams for the simplicity of the more efficient methods used[11].

In this study IHS and ICA methods were implemented to get optimum outputs with less color distortion. To overcome color distortion and non-Gaussian problems image fusion methods with higher order statistics were used to reduces redundant data [12],[13], analysis the non-Gaussian noises of images and separate independent data from redundant MS images.

III. Proposed Method

Image fusion methods are categorized into 2-domains namely transform domain and spatial domain [14]. Since the regions or pixels are selected without intermediate process in a spatial domain, it is known as single- scale fusion technique.

The spatial domain based technique is to take the maximum or minimum, average of the images pixel by pixel. However, its simplicity, this method can causes some side effects such as the introducing noise, reduced contrast and artifacts [14].To overcome the drawbacks of spatial domain method, transform domain method is exploited. To improve quality of the fused image with less complexity, an effective image fusion method is proposed in this paper.

The proposed fusion technique is as represented in Fig.1. The steps in the proposed fusion method are as follows:

Fig. 1: Block Diagram of Proposed Method

(1) The source images should be aligned geometrically to each other. These images are assumed to be registered in the pre-processing and have the same resolution.

(2) Source images are to be decomposed into the wavelet coefficients by applying the DWT.

(3) Decomposed coefficients of every sub-band of two source images are to be divided into 8x8 blocks.

(4) A selection standard is then imposed to the LL band, in order to clearly differentiate between focused and blurred regions of the image and to decrease the complexity of overall fusion method. Local Correlation Model calculates the sharpness and clarity of the image. A larger value represents the higher degree of closeness with original image. LCM is computed for all 8x8 blocks using the expression:

$$M_k^{low} = a_k X P^{low} + b_k + e_k \quad (1)$$

$$e_k = M_k^{low} - a_k X P^{low} - b_k \quad (2)$$

Where a_k , b_k are coefficients and e_k is derived from Local Correlation Model. Here M_k and P are Multispectral and PAN coefficients respectively.

The actual resolution enhancement calculated by using the following formula:

$$F_k = b_k + a_k X P + e_k \quad (3)$$

(5) The LCM values of each blocks are compared and consistency verification is to be utilized to select focused portion of LL band of the fused image.

(6) All other bands are selected with the simple maximum to get other bands of fused image.

(7) Finally, Inverse discrete wavelet transform (IDWT) is to be applied to obtain fully focused fused image.

IV. Simulation Results and Analysis

In the proposed technique, MS image was gathered from L-Band NOAA MS satellite receiver. The existing techniques were verified and the new enhanced fusion images were created using LCM wavelet domain. It exhibited higher performance than some of previous techniques. Spatial domain techniques are very simple and highly focused on the spatial data of the input images but the result in the loss of spectral information. Both spectral and spatial data are necessary for the satellite data analysis[15]

Figure 2a and b are MS and panchromatic images for NOAA satellite images. MS have the combination of the five low-resolution bands, it is difficult to represent the full information with the low resolution, the panchromatic image with high resolution gray level image, Fig. 2c represents Brovey transform image, which is performed in the RGB domain and has the limited band fusion.

Fig 2: (a) NOAA MS Image, (b) Panchromatic Image, (c) Fused brovey transform Image, (d) Fused PCA Image, (e) ICA Image, (f) Wavelet resolution merge with PCA, (g) HIS-ICA fusion image, (h) Wavelet resolution merge Image and (i) Proposed Image (LCM in Wavelet domain).

Table 2: Comparison Results of the Proposed Technique with Existing Methods

Performance Parameter	Original image	Wavelet Resolution	PCA	BTS	BT with ICA	HIS-ICA	ICA	PCA	Proposed Method
CC	1	-0.65123	-0.51234	0.87235	0.56923	0.51234	0.41024	0.46124	0.79289
Entropy	7.68931	7.81212	7.79253	5.89235	6.7214	7.41251	7.71243	7.39124	7.91457
ERGAS	0	19.12657	19.11241	14.8129	16.3241	11.8925	11.5912	11.9123	10.8124
Q-Factor	1	-0.52156	-0.48523	0.65028	0.45219	0.39451	0.39451	0.49513	0.72451
RASE	0	78.12562	77.35603	54.7829	65.9321	47.1158	46.9852	49.1242	42.7143
RMSE	0	96.56283	93.99582	73.1254	80.9562	50.2378	54.1289	54.1893	52.4411
SSIM	1	0.12154	0.11995	0.3924	0.55623	0.4958	0.38451	0.53214	0.56293

Table 2 presents the comparison of different fusion method with proposed technique. The lower ERGAS value, higher the spectral quality of the fused images, the existing techniques, the parameters of the spatial and spectral data entropy, Q-factor, CC and SSIM are not given the sophisticated values, however, ERGAS, RMSE and RASE values were low forgetting both the spatial and spectral data.

The dimensional reduction methods are useful for the multispectral satellite image, when using the same image fused with the panchromatic satellite image with proposed method it yields optimal results compare with previous techniques of Fused PCA, NOAA MSI and ICA techniques.

V. Conclusion and Future Enhancement

The present study has developed fusion enhancement methods for the MS satellite images, Windowing methods are very useful for the image enhancing and processing. The ICA is more efficient than PCA for blind separation of the orthogonal data. Furthermore, the proposed technique is considerably enhancing spatial and spectral values. The proposed fusion technique exhibits the good accuracy for both spectral and spatial resolution values.

In future, enhance the clarity of the fusion image using the combination of IHS with different statistical methods.

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